

Chromatographic Studies on Metal Complexes. Part IV. Palladium(II) Complexes of 1-Amidino-O-alkylureas.

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Filter paper chromatography of $[Pd(AMUH)_2]Cl_2$ (AMUH = 1-amidino-O-methylurea) in aqueous KCl-pyridine developer has helped in the identification of hitherto unknown $[Pd(AMUH)Cl_3]$. The synthesis of $[Pd(AMUH)Cl_3]$ has been accomplished via two routes: (i) palladium(II) promoted addition of methanol to dicyandiamide and (ii) treating $Li_2 [PdCl_4]$ with AMUH.HCl in 1:1 ratio at pH~3.0. A number of other dichloromono (1-amidino-O-alkylurea) palladium(II) compounds have also been synthesized. These compounds readily aquate in dilute solution giving bi-univalent electrolyte conductance values. The isomeric $[Pd(AMUH)_2] [PdCl_4]$ has also been prepared and shown to be different from $[Pd(AMUH)Cl_3]$.

WE describe in this communication a filter paper chromatographic study of bis(1-amidino-O-methylurea) palladium (II) chloride. This study has led to the characterisation of dichloromono (1-amidino-O-methylurea) palladium(II), as also a few other 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complexes of its type.

Experimental

1-Amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate compounds were prepared following Dutta and Ray¹. *Dichloromono (1-amidino-O-methyl/ethylurea) palladium(II)*:

Method A: Palladium chloride (0.44 g) and lithium chloride (0.5 g) were refluxed in methanol (or ethanol, 20 ml). The brown red solution was filtered and to the filtrate dicyandiamide (0.21 g) was added ($PdCl_2$: dicyandiamide in 1:1 mole ratio) and refluxed for 12-14 hr. Crops of a light orange coloured compound separated from time to time and were collected, washed with appropriate cold alcohol and dried in air.

Method B: 1-Amidino-O-methylurea sulphate¹ (0.55 g) in 10 ml water was converted to the hydrochloride by treatment with barium chloride (0.4 g in 5 ml water). This hydrochloride solution was made acidic (pH~3.0) with dilute HCl. This solution was added drop by drop to lithium chloropalladite (0.5 g lithium chloride and 0.5 g palladium chloride in 50 ml water) with stirring when light orange crystalline precipitate of $[Pd(AMUH)Cl_2]$ separated. Similar procedures were adopted for the other 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complexes.

$[Pd(AMUH)_2] [PdCl_4]$: 0.1 g $PdCl_2$ and 0.1 g lithium chloride were heated with 20 ml water, filtered and the filtrate was added to $[Pd(AMUH)_2]Cl_3$ ² (in 10 ml water) at pH~6.5 when a dirty orange red granular precipitate separated. This was cooled, filtered and then washed with cold water and finally with rectified spirit.

$[Pd(Py)_2Cl_2]$: This was prepared by refluxing $PdCl_2$ with pyridine in xylene³. Its solubility being limited the sample was dissolved in the developer solvent prior to putting the spot.

Chromatographic studies: Filter paper chromatography (ascending technique) was adopted. The other experimental details have been discussed elsewhere⁴. Various developers as detailed in the legends to Figures 1 and 2 were used. The complexes were spotted as aqueous solution and were detected by spraying acidified (HCl) solution of rubeanic acid when an orange yellow spot developed.

Palladium was estimated by igniting the complexes to metallic palladium. Nitrogen was determined by combustion and chloride as silver chloride. Equivalent weight was determined by standard procedure⁵.

The infrared spectra upto 650 cm^{-1} were run as KBr pellets at CDRI, Lucknow and upto 250 cm^{-1} at the Ohio State University, Columbus.

Results and Discussion

The present study was aimed at finding the best chromatographic developer for the identification of bis (1-amidino-O-alkylurea) palladium (II) complexes. These complexes were originally obtained by Dutta and coworkers² by interaction of aqueous sodium chloropalladite and aqueous 1-amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate. Following this reported prescription for 1-amidino-O-methylurea complex (with the only modification of using lithium chloropalladite instead of sodium chloropalladite) we obtained a light orange yellow precipitate instead of the reported pale cream coloured precipitate of bis(1-amidino-O-methylurea) palladium(II) sulphate. This orange yellow precipitate on treatment with aqueous barium chloride gave a soluble fraction from which we could isolate pale cream coloured bis (1-amidino-O-methylurea) palladium(II) chloride as reported by Dutta

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and coworkers². Significantly an orange coloured sparingly soluble product still remained with the barium sulphate, which was repeatedly extracted with BaCl₂-water and then crystallised. Filter paper chromatography of the pale cream coloured bis(1-amidino-O-methylurea) palladium(II) chloride in aqueous KCl-pyridine developer (70 ml, 0.5M KCl + 30 ml 1 : 1 pyridine, Fig. 1), provided two spots - the one with higher R_f (0.86) was small in size and was of lower intensity than the other with lower R_f (0.51) and of slightly bigger size. This result was rather unusual since bis(biguanide) palladium (II) chloride had provided in the same developer a distinct single spot⁴. This unusual chromatographic behaviour led us to conjecture the following possible equilibrium :

In support of this hypothesis we were happily surprised to see that the orange yellow sparingly soluble product that we mentioned above gave a single spot having the same R_f as the higher one of the two spots shown by [Pd(AMUH)₂]Cl₂ (Fig. 1). An analysis of the orange yellow sparingly soluble product was then completed and it turned out to be [Pd(AMUH)Cl₂]. Large concentration of chloride ion present in the developer possibly facilitated the shifting of the equilibrium (1) towards the mono (1-amidino-O-alkylurea) derivative. *We wish to comment that the synthesis of [Pd(AMUH)₂]Cl₂ is better accomplished on the addition of a few drops of ammonia to the solution of 1-amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate prior to the addition of the chloropalladite.* Under this condition pale cream coloured precipitate of [Pd(AMUH)₂]SO₄ appears in good quantity with very little of the orange yellow sparingly soluble stuff. It is quite likely that ammonia was used in the original synthesis, mention of which was omitted through oversight. It is indeed a fact that all sparingly soluble bis(biguanide) metal(II) sulphates and bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) metal [copper (II), nickel(II)] sulphates are obtained in slightly ammoniacal medium⁶. During reaction of [Pd Cl₄]²⁻ and AMUH. HCl (½H₂SO₄) acid is liberated, which leads to the formation of [Pd(AMUH)Cl₂] to some extent. Addition of a few drops of ammonia obviates the formation of [Pd(AMUH)Cl₂]. It was also verified that the spot with higher R_f was not due to tetrachloropalladite or due to [Pd(py)₂Cl₂], both of which gave R_f almost close to the solvent front (Fig. 1). This is what one would expect on consideration of charge^{7,8}. That bis (biguanide) palladium(II) chloride provides a single spot under the same condition is likely to be associated with its higher stability towards dissociation than the corresponding bis(1-amidino-O-methylurea) complex, as have been verified for copper(II) and nickel(II) systems of the two ligands^{6,9}.

Having thus obtained a clue to the possible existence of hitherto unknown [Pd(AMUH)Cl₂] it now became our obligation to develop a straightforward synthesis for this complex. We have developed two such routes for the purpose. The first method(A) is via palladium(II) promoted addition of alcohol to dicyandiamide. It is now well established that metal ion promoted addition

of alcohol to dicyandiamide leads to the synthesis of 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complexes. So far copper(II)^{1,10} and to a limited extent nickel(II)¹¹ have been found suitable for such reactions. The present study now shows that palladium(II) also can initiate this alcohol addition :

No reaction occurs between dicyandiamide and alcohol in the absence of palladium(II). In fact dicyandiamide can be recovered in over 95% yield even after 50 hr reflux in alcohols.

The second method (B) involves the reaction of [Pd Cl₄]²⁻ and 1-amidino-O-alkylurea chloride in 1:1 ratio in the presence of excess chloride ions at pH ~ 3.0.

Fig. 1. Chromatograms of [Pd(AMUH)₂]Cl₂, [Pd(AMUH)Cl₂], [Pd(py)₂Cl₂] and Li₂[Pd Cl₄] in 70 ml 0.5M KCl + 30 ml 1:1 pyridine.

1—[Pd(AMUH)₂]Cl₂; 2—[Pd(AMUH)Cl₂] via fractional crystallisation of the product obtained by treating orange coloured [Pd(AMUH)₂]SO₄ with BaCl₂ as described in reference² (see text); 3—[Pd(AMUH)Cl₂] obtained by palladium(II) catalysed addition of methanol to dicyandiamide (Method A in experimental); 4—[Pd(AMUH)Cl₂] obtained by Li₂[Pd Cl₄] (1 mole) and AMUH.HCl (1 mole) at pH 3.0 (Method B in experimental).
5—[Pd(py)₂Cl₂]
6—Li₂[Pd Cl₄].

Of these two methods, however, the second method (B) gives better yield. That both these methods of synthesis provided the same complex was revealed by the fact that both these preparations gave a single spot with same R_f (e.g. $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$: $R_f = 0.86$ in 70 ml 0.5M KCl + 30 ml 1:1 pyridine developer, Fig. 1). That palladium(II) does promote addition of alcohol to dicyandiamide giving 1-amidino-O-alkylurea is shown by an inspection of the infrared spectrum of $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$. There is no typical split nitrile ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) band due to dicyandiamide at 2176 and 2222 cm^{-1} , instead a characteristic C-O-R ($\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) stretch appears at 1205 cm^{-1} ¹². The spectra of $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pd}(\text{AEUH})\text{Cl}_2]$ also show bands at 325 cm^{-1} (un-split) and at 312 and 325 cm^{-1} respectively which can be assigned to Pd-Cl stretch^{13,14}. The corresponding Pd-Cl stretch in the compound $[\text{Pd}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_2]$ (dipy = α, α' -dipyridyl) appears at 354 & 343 cm^{-1} ¹⁵. The Pd-N stretch appears at 490 cm^{-1} for both complexes¹⁵. It is an established fact that AMUH is an N-N bidentate^{16,17} donor.

Complexes of the empirical composition $[\text{Pd}(\text{AAUH})\text{Cl}_2]$ are expected to give nonelectrolytic conductance values. Interestingly in aqueous solution at 0.0005M dilution the complexes register biunivalent electrolyte values (Table 2). This indicates that the complexes are rapidly aquated. That indeed this happens is also substantiated by our being able to determine the equivalent weights of the complexes via passage through a H-form cation exchanger column (Table 2). We were unable to find a suitable solvent where the complexes would dissolve without solvolysis. Furthermore, if $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$ behaved as a nonelectrolyte during a chromatographic run we would naturally expect an R_f value almost close to the solvent front. In reality

$[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$ is possibly being chromatographed as one of $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})(\text{py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})(\text{py})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ etc. in aqueous KCl-pyridine developer thus explaining its R_f being lower than that of a nonelectrolyte $[\text{Pd}(\text{py})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, or an anion like $[\text{PdCl}_4]^{2-}$. For a soft acid like palladium(II), partial or total replacement of chloride groups by pyridine seems reasonable. Unfortunately a suitable noncoordinating developer could not be found for chromatographic investigation.

A complex of the composition $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$ can also be written as an ionic isomer $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})_2][\text{PdCl}_4]$. This latter complex was independently prepared (vide experimental) and it turned out that properties of $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})_2][\text{PdCl}_4]$ are much different from those of $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$. $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})_2][\text{PdCl}_4]$ is extremely insoluble in water so much so that we could not even run its chromatogram.

Effect of KCl/Pyridine: Like our previous studies here also as the concentration of KCl or pyridine increases the R_f values of the complex also increases. But pronounced effect is observed in the case of pyridine than with KCl solution. The chromatographic behaviour of $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ in various developers of varying concentrations of pyridine (keeping the KCl concentration constant) have been studied. These studies revealed that as the concentration of pyridine increases (KCl concentration constant), for a fixed time (4 hr) of chromatographic run the solvent front moves to lesser and lesser height (Fig. 2). During these runs the R_f of the upper spot increases gradually (from 0.76 to 0.87) and attain a steady value while that of the lower spot increases sharply from 0.20 till the two spots fuse together to give an overall R_f value 0.85 (Fig. 2,6).

TABLE 1—DICHLOROMONO (1-AMIDINO-O-ALKYLUREA) PALLADIUM(II) COMPLEXES

Methods of synthesis	Alcohol	Complex	% palladium		% nitrogen		% chloride		% water	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
A	CH ₃ OH	$[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$	36.8	36.5	19.3	19.1	23.7	24.1	—	—
B	CH ₃ OH	$[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$	36.8	36.5	19.5	19.1	23.8	24.1	—	—
A	C ₂ H ₅ OH	$[\text{Pd}(\text{AEUH})\text{Cl}_2]$	35.3	34.9	18.4	18.2	23.0	23.1	—	—
B	C ₂ H ₅ OH	$[\text{Pd}(\text{AEUH})\text{Cl}_2]$	34.6	34.9	18.5	18.2	22.9	23.1	—	—
B	n-C ₃ H ₇ OH	$[\text{Pd}(\text{AP}^n\text{UH})\text{Cl}_2]$	33.7	33.4	17.8	17.4	22.1	22.1	—	—
B	iso-C ₄ H ₉ OH	$[\text{Pd}(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	31.4	31.1	16.5	16.3	20.6	20.6	2.6	2.6
—	—	$[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})_2][\text{PdCl}_4] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	34.0	33.4	17.0	17.4	—	—	8.2	8.4

AEUH = 1-amidino-O-ethylurea; APⁿUH = 1-amidino-O-n, propylurea; ABⁱUH = 1-amidino-O-isobutylurea

TABLE 2—CONDUCTANCE, EQUIVALENT WEIGHTS AND R_f VALUES OF $[\text{Pd}(\text{AAUH})\text{Cl}_2]$.

Complex	Molar conductance in water (mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$) at 25°C	Equivalent weight*		R_f : (70 ml 0.5M KCl + 30 ml 1:1 Pyridine)
		Found	Calcd.	
1. $[\text{Pd}(\text{AMUH})\text{Cl}_2]$	204	152	146	0.86
2. $[\text{Pd}(\text{AEUH})\text{Cl}_2]$	214	159	153	0.88
3. $[\text{Pd}(\text{AP}^n\text{UH})\text{Cl}_2]$	211	166	160	0.89
4. $[\text{Pd}(\text{AB}^i\text{UH})\text{Cl}_2]$	170	—	—	0.85

* = Two equivalents of acid per molecule of complex were liberated.

Fig. 2. Chromatograms of $[Pd(AMUH)_2]Cl_2$ in different developers. Total volume 100 ml; KCl concentration 0.1M; pyridine varying: 1—5 ml; 2—10 ml; 3—15 ml; 4—20 ml; 5—25 ml; 6—50 ml pyridine.

It is interesting to note that recently Banerjee and Banerjee¹⁸ have observed during kinetic experiments that a large concentration of chloride ion and a low pH lead to dissociation of bis(biguanide) palladium(II) chloride, $[Pd(BigH)_2]Cl_2$, to dichloromono(biguanide) palladium(II), $[Pd(BigH)Cl_2]$. This latter compound was synthesised and characterised. Biguanides and 1-amidino-O-alkylureas being close in their behaviour^{18,6} as coordinating ligands it is no wonder that dichloromono (1-amidino-O-alkylurea) palladium(II) complexes should also exist. Indeed they do.

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